

ETIOPATHOGENETIC ASPECTS OF DENTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

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The reliability of the research results was determined by the use of modern and tested theoretical and practical methods and approaches, adequate selection of patients, the reliability of the obtained results was confirmed by the use of complementary and interrelated studies. The comparison of the reliability of the obtained results with other results obtained by foreign and domestic authors confirms that our results are reliable and valid, and the conclusions have been confirmed by competent bodies.

The main role in periodontal tissue changes is played by enzymes such as collagenase, elastase, fibrinolysin, chondroitin sulphatase, etc. (Kirsanov A.I., Gorbacheva I.A., Nikolaeva L.A. et al., 1991; Oganyan E.S., 2001; Freeman G., UbackN.-G.5 1998).

The chronification of the odontogenic focus and the development of fibrous changes in the periapical tissues contribute to the disruption of microcirculation in this area (Kirichuk V.F., 2006; Bozkurt F.Y. et al., 2000), which is associated with an important pathogenetic factor in the development of inflammatory diseases along with an increase in the permeability of vascular tissues. is (Risovannyi S.I., 2001; Orehova L.Yu., Lukavenko A.V., Lukavenko A.A., 2004; Orehova L.Yu., Kudryavtseva T.V., Kuchumova E.D. et al., 2005).

Disruption of microcirculation not only plays a key role in the pathogenesis of inflammatory periodontal diseases, but is also associated with it.

The level of their severity (Rakhimova E.N., 2006; Parfenova S.V., 2007) during inflammation, the indicator of vascular tone, peripheral resistance and elasticity of vessels in the microcirculation bed of the periodontium decreases (Zolotarev Yu.B., Guseva I.E., 2001; Kamilov Kh.P., 2002).

To detect disturbances in the microcirculation bed of the periodontium, the method of dopplerography of periodontal vessels is used (Kuchumova E.D., Prokhorova O.V., 2005; Kozlov V.A., Kudryavtseva O.T., 2002; Orehova L.Yu. et al., 2002). This method is based on the Doppler effect, which consists in changing the frequency of the signal reflected from a moving object to a value proportional to the speed of the reflector.

The active factor in the plaque is a protein component that affects the vascular permeability of the periodontal tissue, creates conditions for the formation of the autoimmune component of changes (Loginova N.K., Volozhin A.I., 1995; Orehova L.Yu., Levin M. Ya., Kalinin V.I., 1996; Freidlin I.S., 1996; Anusaksathien O., Polby A.E., 1991; Hillman G., Krause S., Genstersen W., 1999).

Increased permeability of periodontal vessels and the development of vasculitis among the acute virogenic factors noted in the development of gingivitis significantly increase leukocyte migration, which may be one of the reasons for increased lysozyme activity (Pokrovsky V.I. et al., 1994; Orehova L.Yu., Levin M Ya., Sofronov B.N., 1997; Monk-Arquelles D.H., 1995).

Plaque and stone formation processes cannot be explained only by the presence of viral inflammation. The quality and quantity of oral fluid plays the most important role in plaque and stone formation (Ezikiyan G.I., Leontev V.K., Persits et al., 1991; Ghyakonis I.M., Paypalene P.A., 1993). Saliva, as a natural liquid biological environment, plays a major role in the vital

activity of teeth and periodontium, maintaining the homeostasis of the oral cavity. The neutralizing and mineralizing properties of saliva mainly depend on the state of the acid-alkaline balance, the indicator of which is the pH balance. The hydrogen index of mixed saliva is the main natural regulator of the homeostasis of enamel mineral components and the dynamic balance of metabolic processes in the "enamel-saliva" system. The rate of enamel demineralization mainly depends on pH: the lower it is, the faster the demineralization process.

Thus, the reduction of saliva and changes in the composition of saliva lead to various diseases of the oral cavity. The leading role in the emergence and chronic development of various diseases depends on the violation of local and systemic immunity.

Antonova I.N. (2000) found that low concentrations of lysozyme, sIgA, and IgG in the oral fluid of patients with periodontal inflammation are unfavorable prognostically, and professional oral hygiene is considered ineffective in such patients.

In recent years, many studies have been conducted, as a result of which it has been proved that cytokines are involved in the pathogenesis of inflammatory periodontal diseases. It is known that inflammatory periodontal diseases are associated with an increase in anti-inflammatory cytokines, including interferons.

The idea of an autoimmune component in the pathogenesis of periodontal diseases was expressed by researchers in the mid-60s (Burch P.R., Jackson D., 1966), when the assumption that periodontal osteocytes were damaged by autoantibodies was confirmed.

In later work, it is the periodontal tissue complex as a target for immune attack (Anusaksathien O., Dolby A.E., 1991). A significant correlation between the level of periodontal indices and the level of serum autoantibodies to gum antigen was reported by Safarov T. in 1985. during the study of periodontal diseases associated with stomach ulcers.

Fundamental studies that determine the role and place of autoimmunity in periodontal pathology (Orehov L.Yu., Levin M.Ya., Kalinin V.I., 1996; Orehova L.Yu., 1997; Orehova L.Yu. et al., 2000). The significance of the level of autoantibodies to gingival tissues in the pathogenesis of chronic recurrent periodontitis and their high prognostic value were obtained.

The additional contact of plaque and periodontal tissues leads to the emergence of autoimmune processes with alternative changes in these tissues (Lappin D.F., Kinaue D.E., 1999; Jonsdottir I.H., 2000).

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